

Neuromuscular Adaptation to Exercise

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Introduction

Regular exercise is crucial to maintaining health as it results in a gamut of physiological adaptations in the respiratory, neuromuscular, and cardiovascular human body systems. The adaptations help improve physical performance. The level of adaptation is dependent on the type, intensity, frequency, and duration of exercise as well as the initial fitness level and genetic influence to responsiveness of the body.

Muscular adaptation

Skeletal muscle increases the size of muscles in an effort to adapt to mechanical overload. Resistance training activates a range of signals that initiate new protein creation and muscle fiber enlargement that result in hypertrophy and increase muscle fiber number (Cannon & Cafarelli 2401). The adaptations include increased cross-sectional area of muscles, architectural change including fiber penetration change affecting the output through determination of physiological cross-sectional area, changes in the hypertrophy fiber types at the cellular level including a decrease in Type IIx fiber, and an increase in type IIa fiber as well as strengthened fast twitch muscle fiber with increased shortening speed.

Muscle protein synthesis

Muscles are very sensitive to exercise. The muscular system is among the most dynamic systems with degradation and synthesis of proteins. This is achieved by an increased rate of synthesis or a decreased degrading rate or a combination of both phenomena. The adaptation of

muscles is dependent on the availability of nutrition. The synthesis of protein as well as the post exercise response breakdown is adjustable by regulating certain nutrient availability. The ingestion of amino acids and resistance training increase the rate of synthesis of proteins. Combination of the two factors increases the effect due to the fact that protein consumption after exercise increases the synthesis of proteins but suppresses their breakdown. Protein breakdown suppression increases the levels of insulin which helps in further suppression of breakdown of proteins. Maintenance of adequate nutrition maximizes resistance training benefit.

Satellite cell adaptation

These cells specialize muscle stem cells in the niche between basal lamina and muscle fiber sarcolemma and help in skeletal muscle growth and repair and are activated by sufficient exercise or damage of muscles. The cells proliferate, differentiate and fuse to existent myofiber and form new contractile proteins and repair damages. Resistance training increases satellite cell numbers within a few days exercise; further 30% increase over a longer period and remain high even after stopping training.

High resistance strength training adaptation

Progressive resistance training increases the power, strength and size of muscles through muscular contraction and relies on the overload principle in which working and exercise stimulates muscle growth and strength. The neural adaptations to this type of training include the increased central (High brain center) drive after resistance training which serves to increase strength, increased Motor Unit synchronization, decreased force threshold within which Motor Units are recruited, increased Motor Unit firing rate and after training decreased co-activation level of a antagonist muscles.

Muscular adaptation to this type of training requires adjustment of the skeletal muscles to mechanical overload through muscle size increase. High intensity exercise characterized by power strength and hypertrophy bring about many adaptations as they need a massive integration and coordination of musculature to handle the intensive exercise. A number of physiological adaptation to high intensity exercise take place, such as the increase in the size of fiber and muscle as a result of increased number and thickness of actin and myosin filaments, myofibrils and sarcoplasm. High intensity training causes fast twitch fiber contractions and hence improves certain fast twitch function under training. The nerve-muscle connections are also adapted in the way that there is an increased additional motor unit improvement responding in a simultaneous way to improve the production of force, increased synergy muscle activation to support the production of force for speed, strength, power and hypertrophy and increased efficiency of the neural pathways between target muscles. There is also increased contraction timing coordination to meet generation of force (Cannon & Cafarelli 2397). There is also an improved ability of motor unit summation with high intensity training as they need maximum target muscle activation for maximum creation of force. To mitigate neuromuscular fatigue, there is an effective multiple body segment integration to create strenuous movements requiring more involvement of neuro-muscles to resist fatigue.

Longer duration exercise adaptations

There is an increase in the number of muscle capillaries that allow more oxygen delivery to working muscles and absorption of CO₂ into the blood to improve performance endurance. There is also an increased ability of the liver and muscles to store substrates such as the carbohydrates and fat to be used for easy production of ATP. The slow twitch fibers increase in dominance as the exercise duration lengthens. Aerobic, anaerobic fitness and muscular

endurance exercise improve slow twitch fiber function. There is also an increase in the number of mitochondria for increased production of ATP for aerobic metabolism resulting in less lactate produced during exercises below the lactate and aerobic threshold.

Adaptation of the motor firing unit

All training types, except flexibility training, improve motor unit firing effectiveness and efficiency through motor learning. Motor units send stimulus to muscles, and the higher the number of times this happens increases the accuracy of sending messages to the right muscles en route and increases the speed and eliminates the delay of messages.

Works Cited

Cannon, R. J., and E. Cafarelli. "Neuromuscular adaptations to training." *Journal of applied physiology* 63.6 (2017): 2396-2402.